

NITRA IN-HABIT PILOT: TESTED SOLUTIONS FOR REPLICATION AND UPSCALING

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1. Participatory site-specific art residency as an engagement, co-design tool and an inclusive art and urban intervention

A participatory site-specific art residency involves artists working directly within a community or urban environment to create contextually relevant art interventions. It integrates local narratives, urban challenges, and community aspirations into creative works. The approach blends co-design methodologies with art-based urban interventions, fostering participatory public space development.

Description of the process in Nitra pilot:

The first participatory site-specific art residency was conducted at Hidepark in 2022, involving 24 participants in the co-design and co-creation of a large-scale land art installation. Three more were organised in 2023, 2024 and 2025. The first one was conducted with a Slovak artist, the second with two Greek artists, the third with an artistic collective of art students from the Czech Republic and the final one with a Slovak artist/landscape architect. The residency was integrated into broader community activities, including workshops, co-deployment of art interventions, and public presentations.

The final artworks of the first residency were unveiled during the “Climate Connects Us” event, which attracted around 300

attendees. For the two in 2023 and 2024, the results were demonstrated during the Sunday Chill events, which were also a larger-scale intervention developed in the Nitra pilot. And the final in 2025 was unveiled during a Pecha Kucha event.

Suggested implementers:

- Municipal and cultural institutions
- Urban planners and architects
- NGOs focused on community-driven urban development
- Art and design schools
- Independent artists and collectives

Inclusive health and wellbeing outcomes:

- Fosters a sense of belonging and ownership over public spaces
- Provides a platform for cultural expression and diversity.
- Enhances mental well-being through active, creative engagement.
- Encourages active participation in shaping local environments.

Added value to the implementers:

- Demonstrates innovative approaches to community-driven urban renewal.
- Attracts media attention and cultural tourism.
- Enhances placemaking strategies and urban aesthetic quality (for example may decrease instances of vandalism in public spaces where this is prevalent)

Added value to the participants:

- Direct involvement in shaping and transforming public spaces.
- Acquisition of new artistic and co-design skills.
- Strengthened community ties through collaborative creativity. Increased representation in the urban cultural landscape when involving marginalised groups

Personnel effort needed:

- Lead artist(s) for designing and guiding the residency (we selected them through an open call)
- Community coordinators for outreach and facilitation
- Technical experts for material sourcing and installation
- Event organizers for public presentations and exhibitions

Other costs associated with implementation:

- Artist stipends and material costs for installations
- Rental or acquisition of workspace/studio space
- Public event costs (marketing, venue, logistics)
- Documentation and evaluation expenses (in case the intervention requires permits from the public authorities)

2. Participatory photography as an engagement, co-design tool and an inclusive art, education and therapeutic solution

Participatory photography is a visual storytelling method that enables individuals, particularly from marginalized backgrounds, to document their experiences and perspectives. It can be a powerful engagement tool, fostering discussions on urban environments, inclusion, and community needs. The process typically involves training workshops, community photo walks, discussions, and public exhibitions.

Description of the process in Nitra pilot:

The participatory photography initiative was launched as part of the IN-HABIT project in Nitra with a specific target of Ukrainian refugees and people with disabilities. Participants were provided with simple-to-use photographic cameras (they were gifted the cameras) and received basic training in photography techniques. Several group photo sessions were held to capture aspects of participants' lives, focusing on their experiences within the city, project-related activities, and especially their positive and negative experiences in Nitra's public places. The final images were exhibited during the city visit in September 2023 and at selected locations along the cycling corridor.

Suggested implementers (who could possibly replicate):

- Municipalities and local governments
- NGOs and community organizations
- Educational institutions (schools, universities, art programs)
- Cultural centres and social enterprises

Inclusive health and wellbeing outcomes:

- Enhances social inclusion by giving a voice to underrepresented groups.
- Strengthens mental health and wellbeing through creative expression and storytelling.
- Builds community cohesion by fostering mutual understanding across different groups.
- Provides a therapeutic outlet for trauma-affected individuals.

Added value to the implementers:

- Creates an innovative method for community engagement and co-design.
- Generates visual material for urban planning and policy discussions
- Strengthens relationships between local governments and communities.
- Supports evidence-based policymaking on inclusivity and accessibility (for example identification of public spaces and locations with accessibility issues for specific user groups)

Added value to the participants:

- Empowers individuals to share their experiences and perspectives.
- Provides an opportunity to develop creative and technical skills (this was a strong positive outcome expressed by the participants)
- Facilitates social bonding and interaction with different community members (this was a strong positive outcome expressed by the participants)
- Increases self-esteem and recognition of personal narratives in public discourse.

Personnel effort needed:

- One or more trained photography instructors/facilitators.
- Community coordinators to engage target groups.
- Exhibition organizers for curating and displaying images (this is an important point, the participants evaluated the outcomes more positively if their results were also exhibited, suggesting that this aspect can be an amplifier of the positive impacts generated by the solution)

Other costs associated with implementation:

- Purchase or rental of cameras and accessories (we gifted them the cameras, this was also a strong point in positive evaluation as they saw it as something that they have as a keepsake from the events)
- Printing and framing of photographs for exhibition.
- Venue rental for exhibitions and community events.
- Facilitators' fees and administrative costs.

3. BioBlitz Combined with Participatory Phytosociological Analysis as an Inclusive Co-Design and Environmental Education Tool

Developed as an innovative educational and co-design methodology that introduces children to local biodiversity while directly informing the ecological design of public spaces. By combining nature-based learning, field research, and participatory planning, the approach enables children to actively explore natural environments, collect data, and co-create knowledge that directly contributes to the choice of plant and trees composition.

Description of the process in the Nitra pilot:

The phytosociological analysis was organised in collaboration with ecologists, landscape architects, teachers, and community facilitators to map biodiversity in areas targeted for IN-HABIT interventions, including the Picnic Meadow. The activity involved Roma children from the segregated elementary school in Dražovce and pupils from one mainstream city school, creating a rare opportunity for shared participation between socially divided groups. During the events, children engaged in hands-on species identification supported by ecologists and teachers. The findings from these sessions directly informed the planting concepts and ecological design strategies for several IN-HABIT spaces, ensuring that the new green infrastructure supported local biodiversity. The process also fostered informal learning and dialogue between children, teachers, and experts, contributing to greater

environmental awareness and trust-building between segregated communities.

Suggested implementers (who could possibly replicate):

- Municipalities and local governments developing biodiversity-friendly public spaces
- Environmental NGOs and ecological education centres
- Schools and universities implementing outdoor, nature-based learning
- Community-based organisations promoting integration and inclusion through environmental activities

Inclusive health and wellbeing outcomes:

- Enhances psychological wellbeing by connecting children with nature through playful and hands-on activities.
- Builds environmental awareness and fosters early ecological stewardship.
- Encourages positive interactions between socially segregated groups, reducing prejudice and fostering empathy.
- Supports inclusive participation of vulnerable groups in co-design processes.

Added value to the implementers:

- Generates evidence-based ecological insights directly applicable to green infrastructure design.
- Establishes innovative, low-cost tools for engaging marginalised communities in planning.
- Strengthens cooperation between schools, municipalities, NGOs, and academia.
- Offers a replicable model for linking biodiversity education with participatory design.

Added value to the participants:

- Provides experiential learning about plants, habitats, and ecosystems.
- Strengthens collaboration and social integration between Roma and non-Roma children.
- Builds curiosity, observational skills, and self-confidence through discovery-based learning.
- Encourages a sense of ownership and belonging in relation to newly designed public spaces.

Personnel effort needed:

- Ecologists, botanists, and phytosociologists to lead data collection and biodiversity analysis.
- Community facilitators to coordinate outreach with schools and families.
- Teachers and volunteers to support fieldwork and learning activities.

Other costs associated with implementation:

- Educational field kits and biodiversity mapping materials.
- Visual aids and learning materials adapted for children of different literacy levels.
- Logistics and transport for children from schools to field locations.

4. Community bike-sharing as a sustainable and inclusive business model, a community alternative to bike-sharing services provided by public authorities

There is a growing demand in urban areas seeking affordable, sustainable transport solutions that align with green mobility goals, particularly in cities aiming to involve communities more actively in promoting active lifestyles. This business model relies on using community resources rather than a large initial investment, suitable for deployment on a neighbourhood level, especially in marginalised communities.

Description of Nitra case:

The community bikesharing service provides access to bicycles made from spare parts based on seasonal leases, supporting sustainable mobility. It includes a bike repair workshop to ensure functionality and engage users in maintaining the service, where several bike-repair workshops were held. It is based out of Hidepark, an IN-HABIT consortium member.

Suggested implementers:

- Municipalities and local governments
- NGOs promoting sustainable transport
- Universities and educational institutions

Added value to the implementers:

- Demonstrates commitment to sustainable urban mobility and climate goals, also production and resource use sustainability
- Strengthens collaboration between public institutions and community initiatives.
- Provides a more cost-effective solution to classical bike-sharing services (however, if implemented by a public body, it's cost-effective only in partnership with community initiatives)

Added value to the participants:

- Increases mobility options for individuals without personal vehicles.
- Offers a cheaper alternative to regular bike-sharing.
- Encourages healthier, active lifestyles and practical skills when involved in workshops.
- Strengthens community engagement through shared cycling networks.

Personnel effort needed:

- One or more bicycle maintenance staff or volunteers.
- One person coordinating the leasing and communication with participants

Other costs associated with implementation:

- Purchase or refurbishment of bicycle parts (here, costs can be lowered by partnering with waste collection companies or recycling companies)
- Maintenance and repair costs.
- Promotion and user engagement campaigns.
- Possible software or app development for rental system management (in Nitra's case, it is simple website form-based)

5. Slow Impact Incremental Design as a Participatory Urban Planning Methodology for Sensitive Communities

It's a long-term, participatory methodology for shaping public space in communities where rapid change may be counterproductive or even harmful. It does not rely on standard participatory design techniques or fully defined spatial plans but instead fosters continuous dialogue, capacity-building, and iterative co-design. The method is particularly relevant for areas with a history of distrust towards institutions, intergenerational exclusion, or socio-spatial marginalisation – e.g. Roma communities, refugees, and people facing poverty or poor living conditions.

Description of the process in the Nitra pilot:

This approach was piloted in the urban margin of Dražovce with low-threshold engagement activities, trust-building events and creative participatory tools. These included informal cultural and community events doubling as data collection, art-therapy exercises, and establishment of school club at the segregated Roma elementary school, that met every other Friday for different workshops and activities. Rather than preparing a finished project design and then seeking approval, the team deployed small, highly visible, and low-cost interventions as trust-building tools. These micro-steps were co-developed with children, NGOs, and informal community leaders. One Friday they were building mini raised-bed gardens and bug hotels, the next day they were introduced to theatre workshops. These helped to materialise progress while

creating space for learning and feedback. Over time, the intervention scaled to include new public green spaces, play elements, and permanent improvements. The co-design process evolved into a co-management model with local actors, transforming the space into a dynamic outdoor classroom. This approach encourages experimentation and learning by doing – allowing for mistakes (in settings where those are bound to happen) without penalty and fostering a supportive environment for the most vulnerable of populations. The process also influenced long-term curricular innovation, making this model applicable for cities seeking to initiate transformation in socially and politically sensitive environments.

Suggested implementers:

- Municipalities seeking engagement in socially complex or marginalised areas
- NGOs and grassroots organisations working in excluded communities
- Educational institutions and planning/architecture schools using living labs
- Community mediators and facilitators operating in intercultural settings

Inclusive health and wellbeing outcomes:

- Builds psychological safety by avoiding overwhelming, top-down changes
- Supports mental well-being through predictable, gradual transformation
- Fosters community belonging and long-term stewardship

Added value to the implementers:

- Helps avoid failed or resisted interventions by validating solutions through lived experience
- Reduces political risk by making adjustments visible and iterative
- Creates durable social capital through trust-building

Added value to the participants:

- Fosters agency and ownership by placing residents in the role of co-creators
- Reduces fear of change by allowing time to adapt and influence outcomes
- Validates lived experiences and alternative knowledge in shaping space

Personnel effort needed:

- Long-term commitment of facilitators and community connectors
- Design professionals with strong interpersonal and intercultural skills
- Flexible project managers willing to work outside of rigid implementation plans
- Trusted community members engaged as mediators and translators of intent

Other costs associated with implementation:

- Low initial costs for micro-interventions (materials, basic infrastructure, engagement tools)
- Ongoing costs for facilitation, monitoring, and community activities
- Potential need for flexible funding models allowing adaptive design and emergent outcomes

6. Adaptive Urban Furniture Add-on as a low-cost solution to increase accessibility of modern urban seating furniture

Across urban areas, modern seating often lacks ergonomic enhancements, making it difficult for seniors or people with mobility limitations to sit down and stand up safely. This design intervention introduces an affordable, adaptable, and non-invasive solution that improves the functionality of urban furniture. The metal add-on serves as an additional support feature, making public seating more inclusive and user-friendly.

Description of the process in Nitra pilot:

In the Nitra pilot, the add-on for seating furniture was designed as a multifunctional element crafted from metal, allowing for customisation based on users' mobility and ergonomic needs. This addition aims to improve accessibility and comfort in urban spaces without requiring the replacement of existing seating infrastructure. The process involved assessing key locations where public seating lacked ergonomic elements such as backrests or arm supports and engaging with potential users, particularly seniors and individuals with mobility challenges, to co-design the most effective solution. Design is a product of IN-HABIT Co-design Atelier, where participants were landscape architecture students. We are seeking to register it as a design or industrial design.

Suggested implementers:

- Municipalities and local governments seeking to enhance urban inclusivity
- Urban furniture manufacturers looking to integrate inclusive design principles
- Public space designers and planners focusing on accessibility
- Private individuals

Added value to the implementers:

- *Cost-effective urban improvement: The add-on enhances existing seating infrastructure without requiring costly replacements.*
- *Compliance with accessibility standards: Helps cities and institutions align with universal design and inclusivity policies.*
- *Positive public perception: Demonstrates a commitment to age-friendly and accessible urban planning, strengthening community trust.*

Added value to the participants:

- *Enhanced independence and autonomy for seniors and individuals with mobility challenges*
- *Greater comfort and usability: the ergonomic design reduces strain and enhances the overall experience of using public spaces.*

Personnel effort needed:

- *Just for Installation and maintenance, which can be handled by non-specialised municipal workers or urban furniture providers*

Other costs associated with implementation:

- *The production of the prototypes cost 400-640 EUR for one element, but that included testing materials and production processes.*

7. Flood-Proof Countersunk Public Grills for Public Spaces, as innovative urban facilities to create engaging but also safe places in flood-prone areas

Flood-prone urban areas and parks face challenges in maintaining functional and weather-resilient communal spaces. Traditional public grills require elevated concrete platforms, which contribute to soil sealing, disrupt natural drainage patterns, and reduce green space permeability. This design countersinks the grilling area into the natural landscape, allowing it to withstand occasional flooding without damage or functional loss. By relying on terrain modulation rather than built structures, the solution enhances public infrastructure while ensuring ecological balance and sustainability.

Description of the process in Nitra pilot:

While in the process of co-designing public space interventions, we encountered an issue with a location that was already frequented by citizens, although it was a part of the Nitra River floodway. The Slovak Waterways Management Company (under the Ministry of Environment), which manages all the water resources in the country, prohibits any interventions or placing of urban furniture in such areas. During the co-design phase, we managed to arrive at a compromise by introducing the flood-proof countersunk public grills, an innovative infrastructure feature designed to enhance communal outdoor spaces, particularly in areas prone to seasonal flooding. This concept was piloted in Nitra as a nature-based

solution, integrating flood resilience, social engagement, and environmental sustainability.

The implementation process involved:

1. Collaborating with landscape architects to integrate the grills seamlessly into the terrain.
2. Negotiating with several public authorities to arrive at a permit-issuing process for something that was not possible before.
3. Engineering durable, corrosion-resistant materials to withstand repeated flooding.
4. Testing community engagement by promoting outdoor social activities around the installed units.

Suggested implementers:

- Municipalities and urban planners in flood-prone cities
- Architects and landscape designers specializing in resilient urban infrastructure

Added value to the implementers:

- *Low-impact, environmentally sensitive infrastructure that aligns with urban climate adaptation strategies.*
- *Cost-efficient compared to traditional built solutions, reducing the need for frequent maintenance and structural reinforcement (but higher initial costs)*
- *Enhances urban resilience by introducing flood-proof, durable communal infrastructure without the drawbacks of concrete construction.*

- *Improves city branding and community satisfaction, positioning municipalities as leaders in sustainable urban development.*

Added value to the participants:

- *Ensures year-round usability, even in flood-prone seasons*
- *Supports local environmental awareness as residents engage with a climate-adaptive urban feature.*
- *Increases accessibility to recreational activities in public spaces, benefiting diverse community members.*

Personnel effort needed:

- *Design and engineering expertise to integrate the grill system into varying terrain types.*
- *Community consultation and participatory design to align the infrastructure with user needs.*
- *Maintenance doesn't require any specialised staff*

Other costs associated with implementation:

- *Material costs for durable, flood-resistant grill components (we used Corten steel, but cheaper options could be suitable)*
- *Landscaping and terrain modification expenses to ensure proper drainage and soil stability depending on the substrate and groundwater levels.*
- *In the Nitra pilot case, the cost of materials without the works amounted to 16,140.00 EUR.*

8. Modular, Multifunctional and Reversible Urban Furniture: A Durable, Eco-Inclusive Solution for Vandalism-Prone Urban Areas

Modular urban furniture from plastic terrazzo and reclaimed wood represents a context-sensitive, resilient, and environmentally responsible approach to public space interventions in areas affected by vandalism, misuse, or underutilisation. Developed and prototyped within the Nitra pilot, this solution offers a robust alternative to conventional urban furniture through innovative material use and participatory production processes. It addresses both functional and symbolic dimensions of urban design: combining durability and anti-vandalism logic with creative reuse, environmental education, and community engagement.

Description of the process in Nitra pilot:

Two types of modular furniture elements were developed in parallel:

Plastic terrazzo furniture: These pieces were designed using Terratikon™ – a patented composite material combining concrete with unrecyclable plastic waste and construction debris. Their design logic is based on mass and geometry: they are stable due to their weight rather than anchoring, which allows for repositioning and reversible deployment. Their visual identity evokes sculptural forms through terrazzo-like pigmentation and embedded fragments, distinguishing them from standard grey concrete blocks.

Furniture from reclaimed urban wood: Sourced from storm-felled municipal trees, large monolithic wood pieces were processed into seating and lounging elements. Designed for durability and authenticity, they retain their function even when partially damaged. The production process involved students and volunteers under professional guidance, reinforcing the community and educational aspects of the intervention.

Suggested implementers (who could possibly replicate):

- Municipalities and local governments
- Public space planners and architects
- Waste management or circular economy initiatives
- Community design ateliers

Inclusive health and well-being outcomes:

- Enhances perceived safety and order in neglected or contested public spaces
- Supports age-inclusive and short-term use of space (e.g., for seniors or families)
- Encourages community pride and sense of ownership over locally co-created urban features
- Promotes mental wellbeing through design aesthetics and human-nature material connection

Added value to the implementers:

- *Introduces highly durable and anti-vandalism solutions adaptable to various contexts*
- *Reduces long-term maintenance costs through robust materials and modular placement*
- *Demonstrates circular economy principles using unrecyclable plastics and storm-damaged wood*

- *Builds interdepartmental collaboration (e.g., between urban planning, maintenance services, environment, and culture offices)*

Added value to the participants:

- *Direct involvement in shaping public space through design and prototyping*
- *Exposure to innovative materials and sustainable production techniques*
- *Strengthened community ties and intergenerational collaboration*
- *Recognition of participant contributions through visible, tangible outputs*

Personnel effort needed:

- *Designers and material experts (e.g., working with Terratikon™ or reclaimed wood)*
- *Coordinators to lead participatory design workshops*
- *Municipal staff or volunteers for installation and follow-up maintenance*

Other costs associated with implementation:

- *Production of plastic terrazzo elements (including moulding and pigmentation), higher initial cost, but long-term savings due to durability (approx. 1,200 EUR per one module)*
- *Processing and treatment of reclaimed wood (machining, sanding, finishing)*
- *Transport, placement and potential adaptations to local terrain*
- *Optional costs for public engagement activities or community events during implementation*

3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

13 CLIMATE ACTION

9. Eco-Stabilising Land Art as a Nature-Based Solution for Biodiversity, Well-being, and Environmental Education

The Eco-Stabilising Land Art is an innovative, nature-based installation developed within the IN-HABIT project in Nitra to integrate ecological functionality, aesthetic value, and educational benefits. Constructed from locally sourced deadwood and branches using a unique spiral binding technique, the structure creates microhabitats that attract xylophagous insects dependent on decaying wood, provide nesting opportunities for birds, and form trophic niches that support biodiversity. It combines artistic expression with ecological restoration, creating a multifunctional public element that fosters both environmental and social impacts.

Description of the process in the Nitra pilot:

Co-designed and prototyped through interdisciplinary collaboration, the installation involved students from the Slovak University of Agriculture, landscape architects, designers, florists, local craftsmen, and municipal services. The city played an active role by **supplying wood material** from municipal tree maintenance, **facilitating permits and approvals** for placement along the cycling route, and supporting integration of the installation within broader **green infrastructure and recreational planning frameworks**.

Positioned directly along a popular cycling route, the installation acts as a visual landmark and encourages public interaction with natural processes. It has also been integrated into environmental

education, serving as a demonstration site for schools, university courses, and citizen science monitoring activities.

Suggested implementers:

- Municipalities and local governments
- Landscape architects and urban planners
- NGOs focused on environmental education and biodiversity
- Universities and environmental training centres
- Cultural institutions integrating art and ecology

Inclusive health and well-being outcomes:

- Enhances mental well-being through contact with nature and biodiversity.
- Encourages physical activity by linking educational and recreational experiences along cycling and walking paths.
- Strengthens community identity by combining artistic, ecological, and cultural dimensions.

Added value to the implementers:

- *Introduces an innovative nature-based solution that supports urban biodiversity goals.*
- *Demonstrates low-impact ecological design practices transferable to other contexts.*
- *Serves as an educational tool that increases public awareness of ecosystem processes.*

Added value to the participants:

- *Offers opportunities to co-create multifunctional public spaces.*
- *Increases knowledge and appreciation of biodiversity and ecological processes.*

- *Builds skills in design, prototyping, and environmental monitoring.*

Personnel effort needed:

- *Ecologists or biodiversity experts for habitat design.*
- *Designers or architects for visual and structural aspects.*
- *Municipal staff or volunteers for installation and maintenance.*

Other costs associated with implementation:

- *Material costs can be minimised by using locally sourced natural materials.*
- *Costs may include design facilitation, small construction works on site (anchoring), technical construction and carpentry*
- *Optional costs for monitoring equipment if the installation is used for educational or ecological observation purposes. It is optional and can be supported through partnerships with universities or citizen science programmes.*